

Evaluation

Authors omitted for blind review

In this document, we describe the experiments we have performed by applying our reasoning-based prototype, that implements our AFFECTK framework, to three real KPI systems (denoted as CS1, CS2 and CS3, respectively). With these experiments we aim at assessing such a framework around three different aspects: 1) *evolution information support* (for which, we use CS1), 2) *evolution management* (assessed by means of CS2), and 3) *consistent evolution* (assessed by CS3).

Considerations:

- For simplicity, in these experiments we have considered that the person in charge has decided to apply all traceability aspects (consistency conditions and propagation aspects are always applied in the prototype's transformations). Thus, the Formula transformation invocations include `true` values for parameters associated to decisions T1, T3 and T4. In the case of T2 (storage of the motivation), the motivation itself is passed as a string.
- We note that the KPIs included in the three case studies do not include target elements. For this reason, we have considered targets on our own in all KPIs.
- The experiments have been performed by using the Formula command line interface.

Case study CS1

Reference: J. Bastos, R. Garcia, F. Freire, Indicators for waste prevention and management - measuring circularity, 2019. UrbanWINS project- Innovative Strategic Plans for Urban Waste Reduction and Management. Online at <https://www.urbanwins.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/d2.3-Indicators-for-waste-prevention-and-management.pdf>.

This case study refers to a report that presents a set of indicators on circular economy, waste prevention and management. The report has been developed within the UrbanWINS- Innovative Strategic Plans for Urban Waste Reduction and Management- project. More specifically, it presents 35 *waste indicators* (identified with numbers from 1 to 35) and 25 *circular economy indicators* (identified with numbers from 36 to 60). From those indicators, we have identified 14 atomic and 46 compound indicators.

As advanced previously, we have used this case study to assess the usefulness of the evolution information provided by our prototype (*evolution information support*). More specifically, we have based on several circular economy indicators from those defined in the report and performed several changes to check that the evolution information produced by the prototype (regarding tracing, consistency conditions and propagation aspects) is useful to track the performed changes.

Source KPIs (identified as stated in the report)

NO.	Granularity	Indicator	Calculation	Description
48	Atomic	Imports (Imp)	Mass amount of goods entering the geographic area	Goods entering the economy/territorial unit.
46	Atomic	Exports (Exp)	Mass amount of goods leaving the geographic area	Goods leaving an economy/territorial unit. Can be used to describe the support provided by an urban area to other areas; displays the role of the city in meeting the needs of other system.
41	Atomic	Domestic extraction (DE)	Mass amount of raw material extracted from the natural environment	Input from the natural environment to be used in the economy/territorial unit. DE is the annual amount of raw material (except for water and air) extracted from the natural environment.
40	Compound	Direct material input (DMI)	$DMI = DE + Imp$	Measures the direct input of materials for use into the economy. It can be used to describe the total material needs of an urban area.
42	Compound	Domestic material consumption (DMC)	$DMC = DMI - Exp$	Measures the total amount of material directly used in an economy (excluding indirect flows). It provides the effective quantities of goods consumed in a given area
38	Compound	Dependency on other systems (Dep)	$Dep = Imp/DMI$	This indicates the share of DMI that is from imports. It provides insight on the vulnerability of an urban area the extent to which it is dependent on other outer areas.

We note that the source KPI system consist of three atomic indicators and three compounds.

KPI System in Formula

```
// KPIImp:
KPIImp is KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0)
KPIFormula(1,"",",",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(1,"",",",Atomic),KPIImp)
basicValue(KPIImp,2)
// KPIExp:
KPIExp is KPI(2,"KPIExp",Active,0)
KPIFormula(2,"",",",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(2,"",",",Atomic),KPIExp)
basicValue(KPIExp,3)
// KPIDE:
KPIDE is KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0)
KPIFormula(3,"",",",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(3,"",",",Atomic),KPIDE)
basicValue(KPIDE,4)
//KPIDMI=KPIDE+KPIImp
KPIDMI is KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Active,0)
KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+ ",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+ ",Compound), KPIDMI)
is_based_on(KPIDMI,KPIDE)
is_based_on(KPIDMI,KPIImp)
// KPIDMC = KPIDMI - KPIExp
KPIDMC is KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(5,"KPIDMI-KPIExp","- ",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(5,"KPIDMI-KPIExp","- ",Compound), KPIDMC)
is_based_on(KPIDMC,KPIDMI)
is_based_on(KPIDMC,KPIExp)
// KPIDep = KPIImp/KPIDMI
KPIDep is KPI(6,"KPIDep",Active,0)
KPIFormula(6,"KPIImp/KPIDMI","/",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(6,"KPIImp/KPIDMI","/",Compound), KPIDep)
is_based_on(KPIDep,KPIImp)
is_based_on(KPIDep,KPIDMI)
```

Starting from the previous indicators, we have considered the following two sequential evolution changes.

Experiment 1. Creation of the indicator PTB:

NO.	Granularity	Indicator	Calculation	Description
55	Compound	Physical trade balance (PTB)	PTB= Imp -Exp	Defined as the difference between physical imports and physical exports. A physical trade surplus indicates a net import of materials, whereas a physical trade deficit indicates a net export.

Starting from the previous KPIs, we have considered a new indicator, PTB, defined as $Imp - Exp$. Thus, we have applied the `CreateKPI` transformation, whose implementation is based on the `CreateKPI` pattern in the Supplementary Material [SupMa], using suitable arguments.

Formula instructions¹:

```
//load the specification
load path\AFFECTK\FormulaPrototype\FormulaPrototype.4ml
//Invoke the transformation
transform CreateKPI <"KPIPTB", 7, Compound, "KPIImp-KPIExp", lessThan, 78, -1, "-",
IN.KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0), IN.KPI(2,"KPIExp",Active,0),true, "new needs" > KPISystem
//Show the resulted KPI model
knows CreateKPI#1
```

Formula results:

As a result, Formula has shown that the indicator does not contradict any consistency condition from those implemented by the `CreateKPI` transformation (*nonRepeatedName*, *uniqueness*, and *coherence*). More specifically, the `CreateKPI.conformsTransform` query is evaluated as `true` since queries `CreateKPI.repeatedName`, `CreateKPI.nonUniqueness` and `CreateKPI.incoherence` are evaluated as `false`:

```
Query evaluation results:
CreateKPI.@user_conforms => True
CreateKPI.conformsTransform => True
CreateKPI.incoherence => False
CreateKPI.nonUniqueness => False
CreateKPI.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
```

¹ Since target values are not specified we consider `lessThan 5` for simplicity and `KPITarget` elements are not included in the results.

Additionally, it can be shown that neither the source KPI model (see queries preceded by IN) nor the target KPI model (see queries preceded by out) violate the constraints defined by the Formula domains.

The Formula report also shows the resulting KPI system (including the new KPI in Active state and with 0 as version), together with the corresponding instances related to evolution aspects.

```

1- PACreateKPI1 is PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",CreateKPI,"new needs",Ejecuted)
2- AppliedTraceOperation("",KPI(7,"KPIPTB",Active,0), PACreateKPI1)
3- AppliedPropagationOperation(
  PACreateKPI1,
  PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",UpdateCalculationRule,"InfluencedBy",
    InStudyOptional),
  "Check whether the application of the 'influences' create pattern to the indicated KPI may imply the
    need for applying the 'influenced by' update calculation rule pattern",
  KPI(7,"KPIPTB ",Active,0))
4- AppliedPropagationOperation(
  PACreateKPI1,
  PatternApplication("date","User","no comments", DeleteKPI, "InfluencedBy", InStudyOptional),
  "Check whether the application of the 'influences' create pattern to the indicated KPI may imply the
    need for applying the 'influenced by' delete pattern",
  KPI(7,"KPIPTB ",Active,0))
5- AppliedPropagationOperation(
  PACreateKPI1,
  PatternApplication("date","User","no comments", CreateKPI, "InfluencedBy", InStudyOptional),
  "Check whether the application of the 'influences' create pattern to the indicated KPI may imply the
    need for applying the 'influenced by' creation pattern",
  KPI(7,"KPIPTB ",Active,0))
6- //KPIs definitions, included the new one
  KPIPTB is KPI(7,"KPIPTB",Active,0)
  KPIFormula(7,"KPIImp-KPIImp","-",Compound)
  KPIElement_belongs_to_Version( KPIFormula(7,"KPIImp-KPIExp","-",Compound), KPIPTB)
  is_based_on(KPIPTB,KPIImp)
  is_based_on(KPIPTB,KPIImp)
  ....
  //Derived calculatedValues, relatedKPIs, KPIValue instances, etc.

```

In this report, we can see that all constraints are satisfied (no `AppliedConsistencyCondition` instances are created with the violated constraints).

Additionally, and according to the CreateKPI pattern, the transformation execution informs the user (by means of suitable instances of `AppliedPropagationOperation`) about the propagation actions she/he could take, choosing between: i) modifying the calculation rules of other KPIs as appropriate (line 3), making use of the new KPI, and/or ii) deleting or creating other KPIs, considering the creation of the new KPI (lines 4 and 5, respectively). In this case, since such propagation actions are not needed to maintain the consistency of the KPI system, they are identified as `InStudyOptional`.

Later, based on such suggested propagations and the considered KPI system, we have decided to redefine the indicator DMC so that it includes PTB ($DMC = DE + PTB$), by applying the `UpdateCalculationRule` transformation.

Formula instructions:

```
load path\AFFECTK\FormulaPrototype\FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform UpdateCalculationRule < IN.KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,0), -1, "KPIDE+KPIPTB",
"+",IN.KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0), IN.KPI(7,"KPIPTB",Active,0), true,"Change DMC", true, true> KPISystem
```

As a result, Formula shows that the consistency conditions are satisfied (we note, for example, query `UpdateCalculationRule.conformsTransform => true`, showing that the queries stated by the transformation are evaluated as `false`, and that the `conforms` queries related to both source and target KPI models are also evaluated to `true`:

```
Query evaluation results:
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
UpdateCalculationRule.@user_conforms => True
UpdateCalculationRule.incoherence => False
UpdateCalculationRule.conformsTransform => True
UpdateCalculationRule.nonActiveState => False
UpdateCalculationRule.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
```

In this case, in addition to the reporting information regarding traceability, consistency conditions and propagation aspects, we can also see the evolution of indicator DMC as follows:

- 1- **PAUpdateCR1** is **PatternApplication**("date","User","no comments",UpdateCalculationRule,"change DMC",Ejecuted)
- 2- **AppliedTraceOperation**(
KPIFormula(5,"KPIDMI-KPIExp","-",Compound), KPIFormula(6,"KPIDE+KPIPTB","+",Compound),
PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",
PAUpdateCR1)
- 3- **AppliedPropagationOperation**(
PAUpdateCR1,
PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",UpdateTarget,"InfluencedBy",**InStudyCompulsory**),
"Check whether the application of the 'influences' update calculation rule pattern to the indicated KPI
may imply the need for applying the 'influenced by' update target pattern",
KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,1))

```

4- //KPIs definitions, included the previous and the new version of the indicator DMC
KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Deprecated,0)
KPIFormula(6,"KPIImp/KPIDMI","/",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(5,"KPIDMI-KPIExp","-",Compound),KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Deprecated,0))
is_based_on(KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Deprecated,0),KPI(2,"KPIExp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Deprecated,0),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Active,0))
KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,1)
KPIFormula(6,"KPIDE+KPIPTB","+",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(6,"KPIDE+KPIPTB","+",Compound),KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,1))
is_based_on(KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,1),KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(5,"KPIDMC",Active,1),KPI(7,"KPIPTB",Active,0))

.....
//Derived calculatedValues, relatedKPIs relationships and KPIValue instances

```

As it can be seen in line 3, the application of the `UpdateTarget` transformation is indicated as propagated compulsory action in order to check whether the new calculation rule is coherent with the target or status options of the KPIDMC. As advanced previously, since target aspects are not considered in the definition of the UrbanWINS project indicators, we have not considered this element of KPIs in our experiments.

We also note that, since there is no other KPIs that include indicator DMC in their formulas, the report does not include a `AppliedPropagationOperation` instance to compulsorily propagate a modification of the calculation rule of other indicators.

We also note how both versions of KPI DMC are included: the version previous to the evolution change with “Deprecated” state and version identifier 0, and the current one with “Active” state and version identifier 1.

Experiment 2. Deletion of the indicator DMI:

We have supposed that the indicator DMI is not longer needed in the system and we have applied the `DeleteKPI` transformation.

Formula instructions:

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform DeleteKPI<IN.KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Active,0),true,"no longer collected", true, true> KPISystem
```

Formula results:

As a result, the Formula console has informed us that the *coherence* condition is not satisfied (`incoherence` Formula constraint is true) since there is an indicator that depends on indicator DMI (more specifically, indicator Dep).

```
Query evaluation results:
DeleteKPI.@user_conforms => False
DeleteKPI.incoherence => True
DeleteKPI.conformsTransform => False
DeleteKPI.nonActiveState => False
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodelgranularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodelgranularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
```

The transformation report also shows (by means of the corresponding `AppliedConsistencyCondition` instance) that the query is not satisfied.

Consequently, the transformation report also indicates (by means of the generated `AppliedPropagationOperation` instances) to choose among different compulsory options to maintain the system consistency: i) modifying the calculation rules of the KPI(s) that include the KPI to be deleted (indicator Dep), so that they do not contain the KPI (line 4), or ii) deleting the KPIs that include the KPI to be deleted (line 5). Both actions are identified as `InStudyCompulsory`. Additionally, it suggests the person in charge to assess if she/he wants to delete or create other KPIs, considering the deletion of the KPI (lines 6 and 7). These actions are identified as `InStudyOptional`.

- 1- **PADeleteKPI1** is **PatternApplication("date","User","no comments", DeleteKPI,"no longer collected",Ejecuted)**
- 2- **AppliedTraceOperation**(
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0),
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1),
PADeleteKPI1)
- 3- **AppliedConsistencyCondition**(PADeleteKPI1, KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Active,0), **"incoherence"**)
- 4- **AppliedPropagationOperation**(
PADeleteKPI1,
PatternApplication("date","User","no comments", UpdateCalculationRule, "InfluencedBy",
InStudyCompulsory),
"Calculation rule of the indicated KPI would need to be checked",
KPI(6,"KPIDep",Active,0))
- 5- **AppliedPropagationOperation**(
PADeleteKPI1,
PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",DeleteKPI,"InfluencedBy",**InStudyCompulsory**),
"The indicated KPI could need to be deleted",
KPI(6,"KPIDep",Active,0))
- 6- **AppliedPropagationOperation**(
PADeleteKPI1,
PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",CreateKPI,"InfluencedBy",**InStudyOptional**),
"Check whether the application of the 'influences' delete pattern to the indicated KPI (in the Deleted state) may imply the need for applying the 'influenced by' create pattern",
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1))
- 7- **AppliedPropagationOperation**(
PADeleteKPI1,
PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",DeleteKPI,"InfluencedBy",**InStudyOptional**),
"Check whether the application of the 'influences' delete pattern to the indicated KPI (in the Deleted state) may imply the need for applying the 'influenced by' delete pattern",
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1))
- 8- //KPIs definitions, included the previous and the new version of the indicator DMI
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1)
KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+","Compound")
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+","Compound"),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1),KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1),KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0))
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+","Compound"),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0),KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0),KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0))....
//Derived calculatedValues, relatedKPIs, KPIValue instances, etc.

In particular, we have decided to update indicator Dep as propagated change.

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform DeleteKPI<IN.KPI(6,"KPIDep",Active,0),true,"propagated deletion", true, true> KPISystem
```

Formula results:

As a result, the Formula console has informed us that all condition are satisfied.

Query evaluation results:

```
DeleteKPI.@user_conforms => True
DeleteKPI.incoherence => False
DeleteKPI.conformsTransform => True
DeleteKPI.nonActiveState => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
```

The resulted report is:

```
1- PADeleteKPI2 is PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",DeleteKPI,"propagated
deletion",Ejecuted)
2- AppliedTraceOperation(
  KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deprecated,0),
  KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1),
  PADeleteKPI2 )
3- AppliedPropagationOperation(
  PADeleteKPI2,
  PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",CreateKPI,"InfluencedBy",InStudyOptional),
  "Check whether the application of the 'influences' delete pattern to the indicated KPI (in the Deleted
state) may imply the need for applying the 'influenced by' create pattern",
  KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1))
4- AppliedPropagationOperation(
  PADeleteKPI2,
  PatternApplication("date","User","no comments",DeleteKPI,"InfluencedBy",InStudyOptional),
  "Check whether the application of the 'influences' delete pattern to the indicated KPI (in the Deleted
state) may imply the need for applying the 'influenced by' delete pattern",
  KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1))
```

```

5- //KPIs definitions, included the previous and the new version of the KPIDMI
KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1)
KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+",Compound),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1),KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1),KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0))

KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"KPIDE+KPIImp","+",Compound),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0),KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deprecated,0),KPI(3,"KPIDE",Active,0))
.....

KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1)
KPIFormula(6,"KPIImp/KPIDMI","/",Compound)
is_based_on(KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1),KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1))
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(6,"KPIImp/KPIDMI","/",Compound),KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deleted,1))

KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deprecated,0)
is_based_on(KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deprecated,0),KPI(1,"KPIImp",Active,0))
is_based_on(KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deprecated,0),KPI(4,"KPIDMI",Deleted,1))
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(6,"KPIImp/KPIDMI","/",Compound),KPI(6,"KPIDep",Deprecated,0))

//Derived calculatedValues, relatedKPIs, KPIValue instances, etc.

```

Since there is no indicator that depends on Dep, no compulsory propagation actions are indicated. The new version of the indicator `KPIDep` is also shown in the report.

Case study CS2

Reference: IAPT, Improving Access to Psychological Therapies, Key Performance Indicators (IAPT KPIs), 2014. Online at <https://digital.nhs.uk/data-and-information/publications/statistical/improving-access-to-psychological-therapies-key-performance-indicators-iapt-kpis>.

In this case study we use the KPIs officially used in the IAPT (Improving Access to Psychological Therapies, 2014) programme. This program was established in 2008 in order to improve access to Psychological Therapies for people with Depression and Anxiety Disorders. Since then, the program has defined a family of several indicators which have evolved along time. These indicators are composed by KPIs and Headline indicators as an agreed mechanism for measuring patients' progress: while KPIs are at the tactical level of management and control performance, Headline indicators (we refer to them as HIs) are strategic indicators used to support change decisions (they can also be considered as atomic and compound, respectively).

Here, we present the indicators included in the different nine versions published at², as well as the evolution changes they have undergone.

Atomic indicators (KPIs)

1. **KPI1:** Level of Need. It presents the number of people who have depression and/or anxiety disorders in the general adult population. The number presenting population is produced as a result of the Psychiatric Morbidity Survey.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

2. **KPI3a:** The number of people who have been referred for psychological therapies during the reporting quarter.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

3. **KPI3b:** The number of active referrals who have waited more than 28 days from referral to first treatment/first therapeutic session (at the end of the reporting quarter).

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

4. **KPI4:** The number of people who have entered (i.e. received) psychological treatment, (i.e. had their first therapeutic session) during the reported quarter is related to the concept person.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

5. **KPI5:** The number of people who have completed treatment (minimum 2 treatment contacts) during the reporting quarter.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

² <https://digital.nhs.uk/data-and-information/publications/statistical/improving-access-to-psychological-therapies-key-performance-indicators-iapt-kpis>

6. **KPI6a:** The number of people who are “moving to recovery” (of those who have completed treatment, those who at initial assessment achieved "caseness" and at final session did not) during the reporting period.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

7. **KPI6b:** The number of people who have completed treatment not at clinical caseness at initial assessment.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

8. **KPI7:** The number of people moving off sick pay or benefits during the reporting period.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the last one.

Compound indicators (Headline indicators)

9. **HI1(SQU16_04- PHQ13_05):** *Access Rate*. It indicates the people who have entered (i.e. received) treatment as a proportion of people with anxiety or depression. That is, the number of people entering treatment (KPI 4) over the level of need, i.e. the number of people with depression and anxiety disorders in the population (KPI1). It was expressed as $(KPI4/KPI1)*100$.

Evolution aspects:

- 1) From the first version until the fourth one (included) this measure was collected by means of the indicator with name **SQU16_04**. The indicator **SQU16_04** was no longer collected since the fifth version.
- 2) In the fifth version a new indicator with name **PHQ13_05** was created with the same formula as **SQU16_04**. This indicator remains from then until the last version.

10. **HI2 (Recovery rate- PHQ13_06):** *Recovery Rate*. The number of people not at caseness at their last session, as a proportion of people who were at caseness at their first session. That is, the number of people who are moving to recovery (KPI6), divided by the number of people who have completed treatment (KPI5) minus the number of people who have completed treatment that were not at caseness at initial assessment (KPI6b). It is expressed as $(KPI6a/(KPI5-KPI6b))*100$.

Evolution aspects:

- 1) From the first version until the fourth one (included) this measure was collected by means of the indicator with name **Recovery rate**. The indicator **Recovery rate** was no longer collected since the fifth version.
- 2) In the fifth version a new indicator with name **PHQ13_06** was created with the same formula as **Recovery rate**. This indicator remains from then until the last version.

11. **HI3 (SQU16_05):** This indicator is referred to as **SQU16_05**. The proportion of referrals that are entering treatment. It is expressed as $KPI4/KPI3a$.

Evolution aspects: This indicator is collected from the first version until the fourth one (included), from which it is no longer collected.

In order to illustrate the evolution changes along time, we next include a table with this information:

As advanced previously, we have used this case study to evaluate the capacity of our proposal to manage evolution (*evolution management*). More specifically, we have performed the evolution of the indicators defined by the IAPT programme along the different nine published versions.

Evolution management transformations³

- 1) **First version- Creation transformation instructions:** We create from scratch the indicators included in the first version (atomic and compound indicators).

Atomic indicators

```
load path\AFFECTK\FormulaPrototype\FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform CreateKPI <"KPI1", 1, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 2, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI3a", 2, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 4, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI3b", 3, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 2, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI4", 4, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 4, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI5", 5, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 2, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI6a", 61, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 4, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI6b", 62, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 2, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"KPI7", 7, Atomic, "", lessThan, 5, 4, "", "", "", true, "initial version" > KPISystem
```

Result (formatted, without including target, tracing/propagation/consistency aspects)

```
// KPI1:
KPI1 is KPI(1,"KPI1",Active,0)
KPIFormula(1,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(1,"", "", Atomic),KPI1)
basicValue(KPI1,2)
```

³ As in the previous case study, since target values are not specified we consider lessThan 5 for simplicity and KPITarget elements are not included in the results.

```

// KPI3a:
KPI3a is KPI(2,"KPI3a",Active,0)
KPIFormula(2,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(2,"", "", Atomic),KPI3a)
basicValue(KPI3a,4)
// KPI3b:
KPI3b is KPI(3,"KPI3b",Active,0)
KPIFormula(3,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(3,"", "", Atomic),KPI3b)
basicValue(KPI3b,2)
// KPI4:
KPI4 is KPI(4,"KPI4",Active,0)
KPIFormula(4,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"", "", Atomic),KPI4)
basicValue(KPI4,4)
// KPI5:
KPI5 is KPI(5,"KPI5",Active,0)
KPIFormula(5,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(5,"", "", Atomic),KPI5)
basicValue(KPI5,2)
// KPI6a:
KPI6a is KPI(61,"KPI6a",Active,0)
KPIFormula(61,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(61,"", "", Atomic),KPI6a)
basicValue(KPI6a,4)
// KPI6b:
KPI6b is KPI(62,"KPI6b",Active,0)
KPIFormula(62,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(62,"", "", Atomic),KPI6b)
basicValue(KPI6b,2)
// KPI7:
KPI7 is KPI(7,"KPI7",Active,0)
KPIFormula(7,"", "", Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(7,"", "", Atomic),KPI7)
basicValue(KPI7,4)

```

Compound indicators

```

transform CreateKPI <"SQU16_04", 164, Compound, "KPI4/KPI1", lessThan, 5, -1,
"/",IN.KPI(4,"KPI4",Active,0),IN.KPI(1,"KPI1",Active,0),true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"RecoveryRateA", 81, Compound, "KPI5-KPI6b", lessThan, 5, -1, "-"
,IN.KPI(5,"KPI5",Active,0),IN.KPI(62,"KPI6b",Active,0),true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"RecoveryRate", 8, Compound, "KPI6a/RecoveryRateA", lessThan, 5, -1,
"/",IN.KPI(4,"KPI6a",Active,0),IN.KPI(81,"RecoveryRateA",Active,0),true, "initial version" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"SQU16_05", 165, Compound, "KPI4/KPI3a", lessThan, 78, -1,
"/",IN.KPI(4,"KPI4",Active,0),IN.KPI(2,"KPI3a",Active,0),true, "initial version" > KPISystem

```

Result (formatted, without including target, tracing/propagation/consistency aspects)

```

// SQU16_04: KPI4/KPI1.
SQU16_04 is KPI(164,"SQU16_04",Active,0)
KPIFormula(164,"KPI4/KPI1", "/", Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(164,"KPI4/KPI1", "/", Compound), SQU16_04)
is_based_on(SQU16_04,KPI4)
is_based_on(SQU16_04,KPI1)
// RecoveryRate: KPI6/(KPI5-KPI6b).
// RecoveryRatea=KPI5-KPI6b
RecoveryRatea is KPI(81,"RecoveryRatea",Active,0)
KPIFormula(81,"KPI5-KPI6b", "-", Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(81,"KPI5-KPI6b", "-", Compound), RecoveryRatea)
is_based_on(RecoveryRatea,KPI5)
is_based_on(RecoveryRatea,KPI6b)
//RecoveryRate = KPI6/ RecoveryRatea
RecoveryRate is KPI(8,"RecoveryRate",Active,0)
KPIFormula(8,"KPI6a/RecoveryRatea", "/", Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(8,"KPI6a/RecoveryRatea", "/", Compound),RecoveryRate)
is_based_on(RecoveryRate,KPI6a)
is_based_on(RecoveryRate,RecoveryRatea)
// SQU16_05: KPI4/KPI3a.
SQU16_05 is KPI(165,"SQU16_05",Active,0)
KPIFormula(165,"KPI4/KPI3a", "/", Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(165,"KPI4/KPI3a", "/", Compound), SQU16_05)
is_based_on(SQU16_05,KPI4)
is_based_on(SQU16_05,KPI3a)

```

2) Fifth version

Deletion transformation instruction to delete SQU16_04 and creation instructions to create PHQ13_05:

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform DeleteKPI<IN.KPI(164,"SQU16_04",Active,0), true, "no longer collected", true, true> KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"PHQ13_05", 135, Compound, "KPI4/KPI1", lessThan, 5, -1,
"/",IN.KPI(4,"KPI4",Active,0),IN.KPI(1,"KPI1",Active,0),true, "version 5 need" > KPISystem
```

Result (formatted, without including target, tracing/propagation/consistency aspects)

```
// PHQ13_05: KPI4/KPI1.
PHQ13_05 is KPI(135,"PHQ13_05",Active,0)
KPIFormula(135,"KPI4/KPI1","/",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(135,"KPI4/KPI1","/",Compound), PHQ13_05)
is_based_on(PHQ13_05,KPI4)
is_based_on(PHQ13_05,KPI1)
```

Deletion transformation instruction to delete SQU16_05:

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform DeleteKPI<IN.KPI(165,"SQU16_05",Active,0), true, "no longer collected", true, true> KPISystem
```

Deletion transformation instruction to delete RecoveryRate and creation instructions to create PHQ13_06:

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform DeleteKPI<IN.KPI(8,"RecoveryRate",Active,0), true, "no longer collected", true, true> KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <"PHQ13_06a", 1361, Compound, "KPI5-KPI6b", lessThan, 5, -1, "-
",IN.KPI(5,"KPI5",Active,0),IN.KPI(62,"KPI6b",Active,0),true, "Fifth version need" > KPISystem
transform CreateKPI <" PHQ13_06", 136, Compound, "KPI6a/PHQ13_06a", lessThan, 5, -1,
"/",IN.KPI(4,"KPI6a",Active,0),IN.KPI(81," PHQ13_06a",Active,0),true, "Fifth version need" > KPISystem
```

Result (formatted, without including target, tracing/propagation/consistency aspects)

```
// PHQ13_05: KPI6/(KPI5-KPI6b)
//PHQ13_05a=KPI5-KPI6b
PHQ13_05a is KPI(1351,"RecoveryRatea",Active,0)
KPIFormula(1351,"KPI5-KPI6b", "-",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(1351,"KPI5-KPI6b", "-",Compound), PHQ13_05a)
is_based_on(PHQ13_05a,KPI5)
is_based_on(PHQ13_05a,KPI6b)
// PHQ13_05 = KPI6/ PHQ13_05a
PHQ13_05 is KPI(135,"RecoveryRate",Active,0)
KPIFormula(1358,"KPI6a/PHQ13_05a","/",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(135,"KPI6a/PHQ13_05a","/",Compound),RecoveryRate)
is_based_on(RecoveryRate,KPI6a)
is_based_on(RecoveryRate,PHQ13_05a)
```

We obtain, as a result, the final version of the KPI system.

Case study CS3

Reference: Diamantini, Claudia and Potena, Domenico and Storti, Emanuele, SemPI: A Semantic Framework for the Collaborative Construction and Maintenance of a Shared Dictionary of Performance Indicators. Future Generation Computer Systems 54. DOI: 10.1016/j.future.2015.04.011

In this case study we consider a KPI system formed by 11 indicators obtained from the paper [DiPS16], where authors use this system to illustrate their framework for collaborative construction and maintenance of dictionaries of performance indicators (which, at the same time, is based on the KPIOnto ontology).

The KPI System formed by 11 KPIs (6 atomic and 5 compound) linked by the following formulas (the ID is of our own) is the following:

1. **NH**- NumHours
2. **HC**-HourlyCost
3. **O**- Overhead
4. **TC**- TravelCosts
5. **PTT**- PersonnelTrainingTime
6. **HR**- HourRate
7. **PC**- PersonnelCosts=NumHours*HourlyCost*(Overhead+1) = **NH*HC*(O+1)**
8. **C**- Costs=TravelCosts+PersonnelCosts = **TC+PC**
9. **PTC**- PersonnelTrainingCosts=HourlyCost*PersonnelTrainingTime = **HC*PTT**
10. **TeC**- TeachCosts=PersonnelTrainingTime*HourRate= **PTT*HR**
11. **IED**- InvestmentInEmplDevelopment=PersonnelTrainingCosts+TeachCost = **PTC+TeC**

We have used this case study to show the interest in ensuring evolution changes' consistency by establishing consistency conditions and further consequent propagated changes (*consistent evolution*). More specifically, we have considered several evolution changes to be applied to the KPI system presented in this case study so that they provoked different incoherence situations in the system, some of them requiring consequent propagated changes to be performed to ensure the final system's consistency. These evolution changes have shown the importance of establishing well-defined consistency properties and required consequent propagation patterns to guarantee the KPI system's consistency.

KPI System in Formula

```
KPIBasic1 is KPI(0,"KPIBasic1",Active,0)
KPIFormula(0,"", "",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(0,"", "",Atomic),KPIBasic1)
basicValue(KPIBasic1,1)
//NumHours
KPINH is KPI(1, "KPINH",Active,0)
KPIFormula(1,"", "",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(1,"", "",Atomic),KPINH)
basicValue(KPINH,2)
//HourlyCost
KPIHC is KPI(2,"KPIHC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(2,"", "",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(2,"", "",Atomic),KPIHC)
basicValue(KPIHC,4)
//Overhead
KPIO is KPI(3,"KPIO",Active,0)
KPIFormula(3,"", "",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(3,"", "",Atomic),KPIO)
basicValue(KPIO,5)
```

```

//TravelCosts
KPITC is KPI(4,"KPITC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(4,"",",",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(4,"",",",Atomic),KPITC)
basicValue(KPITC,2)
//PersonnelTrainingTime
KPIPTT is KPI(5,"KPIPTT",Active,0)
KPIFormula(5,"",",",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(5,"",",",Atomic),KPIPTT)
basicValue(KPIPTT,2)
//HourRate
KPIHR is KPI(6,"KPIHR",Active,0)
KPIFormula(6,"",",",Atomic)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(6,"",",",Atomic),KPIHR)
basicValue(KPIHR,2)
//PersonnelCosts=NumHours*HourlyCost*(Overhead+1) = NH*HC*(O+1)
//KPIPCa=O+1
KPIPCa is KPI(71,"KPIPCa",Active,0)
KPIFormula(71,"KPIO+KPIBasic1", "+",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(71,"KPIO+KPIBasic1", "+",Compound),KPIPCa)
is_based_on(KPIPCa,KPIBasic1)
is_based_on(KPIPCa,KPIO)
//KPIPCb=KPIPCa*KPIHC
KPIPCb is KPI(72,"KPIPCb",Active,0)
KPIFormula(72,"KPIPCa*KPIHC", "*",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(72,"KPIPCa*KPIHC", "*",Compound),KPIPCb)
is_based_on(KPIPCb,KPIPCa)
is_based_on(KPIPCb,KPIHC)
KPIPC is KPI(7,"KPIPC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(7,"KPINH*KPIPCb", "*",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(7,"KPINH*KPIPCb", "*",Compound),KPIPC)
is_based_on(KPIPC,KPINH)
is_based_on(KPIPC,KPIPCb)
//C- Costs=TravelCosts+PersonnelCosts = KPITC*KPIPC
KPIC is KPI(8,"KPIC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(8,"KPITC*KPIPC", "*",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(8,"KPITC*KPIPC", "*",Compound),KPIC)
is_based_on(KPIC,KPITC)
is_based_on(KPIC,KPIPC)
//PTC- PersonnelTrainingCosts=HourlyCost*PersonnelTrainingTime = HC*PTT
KPIPTC is KPI(9,"KPIPTC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(9,"KPIHC*KPIPTT", "*",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(9,"KPIHC*KPIPTT", "*",Compound),KPIPTC)
is_based_on(KPIPTC,KPIHC)
is_based_on(KPIPTC,KPIPTT)
//TeC- TeachCosts=PersonnelTrainingTime*HourRate= PTT*HR
KPITeC is KPI(10,"KPITeC",Active,0)
KPIFormula(10,"KPIPTT*KPIHR", "*",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(10,"KPIPTT*KPIHR", "*",Compound),KPITeC)
is_based_on(KPITeC,KPIPTT)
is_based_on(KPITeC,KPIHR)
//IED- InvestmentInEmplDevelopment=PersonnelTrainingCosts+TeachCost = PTC+TC
KPIIED is KPI(11,"KPIIED",Active,0)
KPIFormula(11,"KPIPTC+KPITeC", "+",Compound)
KPIElement_belongs_to_Version(KPIFormula(11,"KPIPTC+KPITeC", "+",Compound),KPIIED)
is_based_on(KPIIED,KPIPTC)
is_based_on(KPIIED,KPITeC)

```

Experiment 1. Modifying a KPI calculation rule so that it causes circular dependencies

Violated constraint: coherence

Context: Given $PTC = HC * PTT$, we update PTC calculation rule so that it depends on IED, for example: $PTC = IED * PTT$

Formula instructions using our transformations, choosing all customizable options regarding traceability aspects:

```
load path\AFFECTK\FormulaPrototype\FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform UpdateCalculationRule < IN.KPI(9,"KPIPTC",Active,0), -1, "KPIIED*KPIPTT",
"*",IN.KPI(11,"KPIIED",Active,0), IN.KPI(5,"KPIPTT",Active,0),true,"motivation change", true,true> KPISystem
```

Formula results (we only include the query results):

Considering that:

UpdateCalculationRule.conformsTransform := !nonUniqueness & !nonActiveState & !incoherence.

Please note the **true** evaluation result of **UpdateCalculationRule.incoherence** and, thus, the **false** value of the **UpdateCalculationRule.conformsTransform** query.

Query evaluation results:

```
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
UpdateCalculationRule.@user_conforms => False
UpdateCalculationRule.incoherence => True
UpdateCalculationRule.conformsTransform => False
UpdateCalculationRule.nonActiveState => False
UpdateCalculationRule.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => True
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
```

Experiment 2. Deletion of a KPI that has others that depend on it

Violated constraint: coherence

Context: Deletion of KPI TC- TravelCosts which is included in the formula of the indicator:

$$C- \text{Costs} = \text{TravelCosts} + \text{PersonnelCosts} = \text{TC} + \text{PC}$$

Formula instructions using our transformations:

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform DeleteKPI<IN.KPI(4,"KPITC",Active,0), true, " motivation change", true, true> KPISystem
```

Formula results (we only include the query results):

Considering that:

DeleteKPI.conformsTransform := !nonActiveState & !incoherence.

Please note the **true** evaluation result of **DeleteKPI.incoherence** and, thus, the **false** value of the **DeleteKPI.conformsTransform** query.

```
Query evaluation results:
DeleteKPI.@user_conforms => False
DeleteKPI.incoherence => True
DeleteKPI.conformsTransform => False
DeleteKPI.nonActiveState => False
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodelgranularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodelgranularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
```

Experiment 3. Introduction of a new PI with the same name as another one

Violated constraint: nonRepeatedName

Context: We create a new indicator identified as C (we repeat the name) with the teach and personnel costs:

$$C\text{- Costs} = \text{TeachCosts} + \text{PersonnelCosts} = \text{TeC} + \text{PC}$$

Formula instructions using our transformations:

Since indicators do not have target, we suppose, as example, that the new KPI must be "lessThan" 78.

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml
transform CreateKPI <"KPIC", 29, Compound, "KPITeC + KPIPC", lessThan, 78, -1,
"+", IN.KPI(10, "KPITeC", Active, 0), IN.KPI(7, "KPIPC", Active, 0), true, "new goals" > KPISystem
```

Formula results (we only include the query results):

Considering that:

CreateKPI.conformsTransform := !incoherence & !repeatedName & !nonUniqueness.

Please note the **true** evaluation result of **CreateKPI.repeatedName** and, thus, the **false** value of the **CreateKPI.conformsTransform** query.

```
Query evaluation results:
CreateKPI.@user_conforms => False
CreateKPI.incoherence => False
CreateKPI.conformsTransform => False
CreateKPI.repeatedName => True
CreateKPI.nonUniqueness => False
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodelgranularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodelgranularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => True
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
```

Experiment 4. Introduction of a new PI with the formula than another one

Violated constraint: uniqueness

Context: We create a new indicator with the same formula as TeC:

TeC- TeachCosts=PersonnelTrainingTime*HourRate= PTT*HR

Formula instructions using our transformations:

```
load path to FormulaPrototype.4ml

transform CreateKPI <"KPINew", 27, Compound, "KPIPTT*KPIHR", lessThan, 78, -1, "+",
IN.KPI(5,"KPIPTT",Active,0), IN.KPI(6,"KPIHR",Active,0),true, "new goals" > KPISystem
```

Formula results (we only include the query results):

Considering that:

CreateKPI.conformsTransform := !incoherence & !repeatedName & !nonUniqueness.

Please note the **true** evaluation result of **CreateKPI.nonUniqueness** and, thus, the **false** value of the **CreateKPI.conformsTransform** query.

```
Query evaluation results:
CreateKPI.@user_conforms => False
CreateKPI.incoherence => False
CreateKPI.conformsTransform => False
CreateKPI.repeatedName => False
CreateKPI.nonUniqueness => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.conforms => True
IN.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
IN.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.base_conforms => False
out.KPIEvolutionMetamodel.conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodel.@user_conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodel.base_conforms => True
out.KPIMetamodel.incoherence => False
out.KPIMetamodel.conforms => False
out.KPIMetamodel.granularity => False
out.KPIMetamodel.repeatedName => False
out.KPIMetamodel.targetExpectations => False
out.KPIMetamodel.nonUniqueness => True
```

Bibliography

[SupMa] KPI evolution patterns. Supplementary material of the AFFECTK Framework. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/4672345>.